

Variation of the Charge of Colloidal Particles. Part II. Effect of Dilution and of Non-electrolytes on the Charge and its Variation with Concentrations of Electrolytes.

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Discussions on the influence of external factors on the coagulating power of an electrolyte centre round certain assumptions regarding the electrical charge of the colloidal particles such as :

- (a) that the charge does not change on dilution,
- (b) that a given rate of coagulation of the same sol by different electrolytes is characterised by a definite value of the potential of the double layer. (Some authors still hold that coagulation takes place at the iso-electric point).

Powis (*Zeit. physical. Chem.*, 1915, 89, 186) postulated that coagulation takes place when the potential falls below a critical value. But he himself observed for arsenious sulphide sol (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 734) that this is not always so. These measurements are not so reliable as those he carried out with oil emulsions, for he used the procedur suggested by Burton which is undoubtedly erroneous (Mukherjee, *Thesis*, (1921), also *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, 103A, 102.). Even the fundamental assumption of a direct relationship between the rate of migration of the particles in an electric field which is taken as a measure of the potential of the double layer and its stability is untenable (for a full criticism see Mukherjee, *Thesis, loc. cit.*, Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1925, 2, 296). Recently Dhar and his co-workers in a number of papers have attempted to classify so-called suspensoid colloids on the basis of their behaviour to coagulation by electrolytes on dilution. In the discussions, they have tacitly assumed that the potential of the double layer on the particles remains constant on dilution though there is scarcely any recorded evidence in support of this assumption.

Attention may also be drawn to the discussions and controversies entered into by Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 20, 1527, also reference to earlier literature), Freundlich and Zeh, (*Zeit. physical Chem.*, 1924, 115, 65) Dhar and Ghosh (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 649; *ibid.* 29, 1925; p. 435,654; *Kolloid. Z.*, 1926, 38, 141) on the influence of non-electrolytes on coagulation by electrolytes and on coagulation by mixtures of electrolytes. The necessity for simultaneous measurements of charges was pointed out by Mukherjee and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 4, 213), and by Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem., Soc.*, 1926, 3, 349). In the present paper the following measurements of charges are recorded:

(a) Variation in the charge on dilution of colloids with water; arsenious sulphide; gold; copper ferrocyanide.

¹(b) Effect of ethyl alcohol on the charge of colloidal arsenious sulphide containing different concentrations of hydrochloric acid.

(c) Effect of different concentrations of the following single electrolytes on the charge of particles of arsenious sulphide sol: hydrochloric acid, sodium, lithium and potassium chlorides, sodium benzoate, sodium citrate, potassium ferrocyanide.

(d) Effect of the following mixtures of electrolytes on the charge of arsenious sulphide sol: sodium chloride and benzoate; sodium chloride and oxalate; sodium chloride and citrate; barium chloride and sodium benzoate; calcium and sodium benzoate, barium and sodium chlorides; magnesium and sodium chlorides, lithium and magnesium chlorides, potassium ferrocyanide and chloride.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In these measurements the cataphoretic method developed by one of us (*Proc. Roy. Soc., loc. cit.*) has been used. It is not possible to make measurements in this place during the rainy season on account of leakage. Attempts have been made to avoid it by insulating all connections and apparatus and by using paraffin oil instead of water in the thermostat. Though the trouble due to leakage can be sensib-

¹ Measurements under this section have been exclusively carried out by Mr. S. G. Chaudhury.

ly diminished, it cannot be eliminated completely and the measurements have to be taken during the cold weather.

Two different glass tubes were used for cataphoresis. The effective distances were measured as usual from conductivity measurements.

One tube had four side tubes and the other two. The effective distance between the two side tubes enclosing the colloid-electrolyte boundary were estimated to be 1.72 cm. and 4.2 cm. respectively for the upward movement of the colloidal particles (direct) and 1.78 cm. and 4.2 cm. respectively for the downward movement (reverse). *On using different tubes one finds some difference in the rate of migration per unit potential gradient.* This should be ascribed to the error in the determination of the effective distance*. The effective distance also varies with the specific conductivity of the electrolyte used for its determination. One gets a constant value and less variation in individual readings when the specific conductivity of the electrolyte is high—(greater than that of $N/200$ hydrochloric acid or $N/100$ copper sulphate). At low concentrations there is a discrepancy probably due to the fact that when the specific resistance is high the electrolyte in the immediate neighbourhood of the electrodes does not uniformly take part in the conduction—*i.e.*, the potential on account of the electrical field is not the same at all points in a plane perpendicular to the axis of the tube. At higher concentrations due to the greater specific conductivity the zone of such irregular fields for the same potential gradient becomes smaller and smaller and the error in the determination of the effective distance becomes less than 1%. The figures for the rate of migration given in this paper (this holds true also for the data in the previous papers of Mukherjee and co-workers) therefore do not represent the absolute value. The cumulative effect of the errors in calculating the effective distance, and consequently the potential gradient, is not however great. So far using six different tubes we have obtained a maximum variation of $\pm 5\%$ from these sources (*vide* Table I for illustration). *The rates of migration have been given in cms. per second per volt per cm. multiplied by 10^6 .*

* Cf. *Proc. Roy. Soc., loc. cit.*, p. 112 ; the following values for the unknown distance in cms. Between the two lowest marks in each limb of the U-tube were obtained by placing the electrodes at different positions and using the same filling of electrolyte for measurements of conductivity ; 17.18, 16.00, 18.22.

TABLE I.

*Same Sample of Arsenious Sulphide Sol with two different Tubes,
Temp. 35°.*

Effective distance between the side limbs in cms.			Rate of migration.		
Tube.	Direct	Reverse	Direct	Reverse	Mean
I	1.72	1.78	50.68	51.4	51.115
II	4.2	4.2	47.29	48.7	48.08

Better agreement between individual measurements is observed when the boundary is in the same level in both the limbs which can be secured by initially using the requisite excess of the upper liquid in the bulb attached to the limb with the side tubes. Under the most satisfactory conditions, namely a sharp boundary and a fairly constant potential gradient the results are reproducible within 1.5% (*vide* Table II).

TABLE II.

*Arsenious Sulphide Sol with a Mixture of .00 N Barium Chloride
and .1134N Sodium Benzoate : Temp. 35°.*

Number of experiment.	Potential Gradient in volt per cm.		Rate of migration.
	Before	After	
1	.9793	.9958	40.6
2	.9787	1.009	40.2
3	.9647	.9960	40.8

The error is mostly due to that involved in reading the position of the boundary. It was found that the correction for the difference in viscosity is negligible when no non-electrolytes were used, in comparison to the error in reading the movement of the boundary. Even in the case of mixtures of electrolytes the variation in

viscosity was very small and varied from '007288 for water (at 85°C) to '007440. The rates of migration were corrected for viscosity differences have been given as 'corrected rate' of migration in the following tables.

The methods of preparation of the colloids and other particulars are given in the following :

(a) *Arsenious Sulphide Sol.*

A saturated solution of arsenious oxide was mixed with twice its volume of conductivity water and the resulting solution was added to an equal volume of the water saturated with hydrogen sulphide which was then passed through the solution until all the arsenic had been transformed into arsenious sulphide. This took about one and half an hour. Then a current of hydrogen was passed till the sol was perfectly free from hydrogen sulphide. The sol was kept in Jena glass bottles wrapped up with black paper in a dark place but as care was not taken to have arsenious acid in excess the presence of polythionic ions cannot be denied (*cf.* Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *loc. cit.*). The sols contained about 16 millimoles of arsenious trisulphide per litre.

In order to secure a uniform electrolytic environment for the colloidal particles as shown by a constancy of the potential gradient before and after the migration, acid of slightly greater specific conductivity in the ratio of 1.04:1 was used for the preparation of the upper liquid. The different samples of arsenious sulphide sol, prepared in the same way showed a considerable difference in the rate of migration per unit potential gradient as also a difference in electrical conductivity (*cf.* Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE III.

Temp. 85°.

Sample No. ...	I	II	III	IV	V.	VI
Rate of migration ...	54.7	52.2	50.8	55.5	61.5	58.5

(b) *Gold Sol.*

The sol was prepared by Zsigmondy's nucleus method (Mukherjee and Papaconstantinou, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1568).

On account of the difference in the density between the intermicellary fluid and the simple aqueous solution which was at first used as the upper liquid it is not possible to secure a stable boundary under such conditions as the colloid runs upwards in streaks. This difficulty however vanished on using the following procedure which also secured a liquid identical in ionic environment with the intermicellary liquid (as shown by the constancy of the potential gradient) and probably also identical with it in composition and density.

The original sol was at first precipitated with barium chloride solution and allowed to settle. The supernatant liquid was alkaline. Its pH was carefully determined from *E.M.F.* measurements. A potassium hydroxide solution having the same pH was prepared in water and formaldehyde and ether were added to it in the same proportion as in the preparation of the sol. The solution was then boiled for a minute, *i.e.*, for the same time as in the preparation of the sol and cooled in a bath of cold water. A solution of potassium chloride of moderate concentration was prepared from portions of this liquid. The requisite quantity of the potassium chloride solution so prepared was added to another portion of the above liquid so that it had a specific conductivity greater than that of the sol in the ratio 1.06:1. The boundary was very sharp and stable and did not give any trouble. The sol had a tendency to settle. The rate of settling was recorded for sometime before and after the application of the electrical field. The rate of settling does not remain uniform. On keeping the tube undisturbed for 12 hours it is found that the boundary at first falls through a short distance and then remains steady. Also it appears that the rate of fall of the boundary after filling the tube depends on the rate at which the colloid level rises in the tube during the filling operation. These peculiarities are probably in part to be referred to local variations in viscosity and density. One might reasonably assume that these factors vary in such a manner during the direct and reverse movements that the mean of the two measurements will give the real rate of migration. Apart from any error inherent in the above assumption one has to remember that the conditions of an *electrically* stable boundary are not satisfied in the case of 'reverse' movements. But from numerous measurements on this and other sols it appears to us that *when the ionic environment is what we have been able to realise in these measurements the*

error involved in this uncertainty is not more than 8%, i.e., the mean may be taken to be correct within 1.5%. The actual data of the settling are also given in the tables dealing with this sol. It should be noted that even in the direct movement the settling was greater than the movement towards the anode for the potential gradients we have employed.

(c) Copper Ferrocyanide Sol.

Nearly equivalent quantities in solution of copper sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide crystals were mixed. The ferrocyanide solution was slightly in excess. The precipitate was filtered, carefully washed and transferred to a beaker. On keeping in contact with pure water overnight it peptised and was then dialysed for about a month and a half. It still contained a trace of ferrocyanide as is to be expected from the well known work of Duclaux.

As the upper liquid we used in this case, an equally conducting potassium chloride solution which gave satisfactory results in agreement with theoretical considerations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

In the following we have taken the mean of the direct and reverse movements to correctly represent the rate of migration. From the constancy of the potential gradient we consider that the electrical environment remains sufficiently uniform and constant during the migration and we think that we are justified in taking the mean of both movements as, the observed rate from the agreement between the two values. Besides the gravitational fall of the particles has always to be taken into consideration. For the arsenious sulphide sol the settling is small.

I. *Effect of Dilution.*

Viscosity corrections were made for all the sols, taking the viscosity of water at the temperature to be unity. In the case of the gold sol only three measurements could be taken because of the low visibility of the boundary at higher dilutions. For the diluted sols the liquid used as upper liquid for the original sample was diluted correspondingly.

TABLE IV.

Arsenious Sulphide

Viscosity of water=0.007283 (35°).

Dilution in ratio of volume of original sol to that of water added to it.	Relative viscosity.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean corrected rate of migration.
pure sol	1.027	60.3	56.7	60.1
1:1	1.023	58.6	56.7	58.9
1:3	1.014	55.8	54.0	55.7
1:10	1.006	17.2	17.4	17.5
1:10	1.005	17.78*	17.2*	
1:20	.998	11.2	11.5	12.2
1:20	.996	12.7*	13.4*	

TABLE V.

Gold Sol. Temp. 35°.

Dilution.	Viscosity.	Time in minutes.	Settling of the boundary in centimeters.		Velocity.		Corrected rate of migration.
			Before.	After.	Direct.	Reverse.	
Pure sol	1.017	20	0.42	0.24	-10.0	41.1	15.8
1:1	1.011	15	0.75	0.25	-31.5	51.7	10.2
1:3	1.01	15	0.33	0.27	-27.6	36.6	5.6

TABLE VI.

Copper Ferrocyanide Sol. Temp. 35°

Dilution.	Viscosity.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean corrected rate of migration.
pure sol	1.415	52.2	47.6	70.6
1:1	1.18	46.5	39.7	50.9
1:3	1.091	44.0	38.9	45.3
1:10	1.04	38.3	29.2	29.9

We observe in each case that the rate of migration per unit potential gradient as also the specific conductivity decreases on dilution. The present measurements have been carried out under more satisfactory and improved conditions than those obtaining in

* Measurement taken after 3 days since mixing

Mukherjee's earlier observations (*loc. cit.*) and there is not the same uncertainty of about 12% in our results. The decrease in the rate of migration of arsenious sulphide sols from 60 to 12 leaves no doubt as to the effect of dilution. The arsenious sulphide sol seems to behave differently from the others in the initial stages of dilution where the rate varies very little at first for this sol, whereas there is a big drop in the other two cases. Assuming that the rate of migration represents the density of the charge we find that for arsenious sulphide sol the concentration of anions (to the primary adsorption of which the charge has to be ascribed) does not suffer marked diminution in the initial stages of dilution. The effect of the observed diminution in the charge will be to make the sol unstable on dilution against coagulation by electrolytes. Mukherjee and Sen (see also Kruyt and Spek) first pointed out that arsenious sulphide sols on dilution show a diminution in stability against precipitation by trivalent and an increase against univalent cations. They also found that depending on the extent of dilution the sol showed a diminution or increase in stability against (divalent) barium ion. Burton and Bishop (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, 24, 701) who later generally confirmed the above observations, tried to classify the electrolytes on the basis of the valency of the cations. This is evidently erroneous as appears from the behaviour of the sol against precipitation by barium ions. The diminution in stability observed against trivalent cations has been explained by Mukherjee and Kruyt on the ground that on dilution the colloid-liquid interface also diminishes. The decrease in the charge on dilution we have observed would diminish the stability and the increase in distance on dilution would act oppositely. But these factors would act in the same manner for different electrolytes. The explanation of the behaviour of the sol in the presence of trivalent cations referred to above thus remains valid. It has been argued by Weiser and Dhar that the adsorption of both chloride and potassium ions is considerable and that on dilution the ratio of the adsorption of chlorine to potassium ions becomes greater so that the negative charge of the particles is greater for a diluted sol. Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 198) in fact, have analytically measured the simultaneous adsorption of copper and chlorine ions in the case of positively charged manganese dioxide sol and found that "the ratio of the amount of adsorption of cupric ion to that of chlorine ion is greater" with a diluted sol than the concentrated one. On account

of analytical difficulties, we think that this indirect evidence is not satisfactory and that direct measurements of the charge are necessary. Such measurements are in progress.

II. Effect of Non-electrolytes on the Charge of Arsenious Sulphide Sol (S. G. C.)

Preliminary measurements have been taken with ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol and *iso*-amyl alcohol. The upper liquid taken, was hydrochloric acid of slightly greater conductivity than that of the colloid with the same percentage of alcohol. Under these conditions the potential gradient before and after the movement of the boundary remained constant and the colloid-liquid boundary was very sharp. In considering the effect of the addition of non-electrolytes, the consequent variation in the osmotic and activity co-efficients of the electrolytes have to be taken into consideration. Besides it has to be remembered that the initial rate of migration on the addition of the non-electrolytes and in the absence of electrolytes is different. Further in interpreting the influence of non-electrolytes, the effect of the change in the di-electric constant both in the bulk and in the double layer (the two are perhaps not the same; cf Born, *Z. Physik*, 1920, 1, 45, 221; Debeye and Macaulay, *Annual Reports, Chem. Soc., London*, 1925, p. 35; 1926, p. 128) have to be taken into consideration. We give below some observations which go to show that ethyl alcohol diminishes the rate of migration. Because of the theoretical interest of such measurements a detailed investigation is in progress.

TABLE VII.

Concentration of hydrochloric acid = 0.0168N.

Ethyl alcohol	Corrected rate of migration
0.	43.5
2½	38.7
5	35

TABLE VIII.

Concentration of hydrochloric acid = 0.0079 N.

% of Ethyl alcohol (by volume)	Corrected rate of migration
0	47.3
2½	46.5
5	44.4
10	40.3

III. *Variation of the Charge of Arsenious Sulphide Sol with Concentrations of single Electrolytes :*

TABLE IX*

Hydrochloric acid. Temp. 35°.

Concentration of electrolyte	Rate of migration		
	Direct	Reverse	Mean
0	54.5	49.5	52.0
.001 N	50.9	45.2	48.1
.002 N	40.9	45.9	48.4
.004 N	38.7	44.5	41.6
.01 N	39.4	42.8	40.8

TABLE X

Potassium Chloride. Temp. 85°.

Electrolyte concentration.	Rate of migration		
	Direct	Reverse	Mean
0	54.7	56	55.4
.000025 N	55.6	51.5 (?)	53.6
.00005 N	50.2	52.8	51.5
.0001 N	49.3	51.7	50.5
.0002 N	44.2	45.1	44.6
.001 N	40.6	43.9 (?)	42.3
.002 N	38.6	40.6	39.6
.01 N	36.6	37.2	36.9
.02 N	33.1	35.4	34.3

* The measurements with hydrochloric acid were not as satisfactory as could be realised. This is evident from the greater difference between the direct and reverse movements.

TABLE XI.

Sodium Benzoate. Temp. 35°

Electrolyte concentration	Rate of migration		
	Direct	Reverse	Mean
0	52.2	54.0	53.1
0.0005 N	54.2	53.1	53.7
0.001 N	57.1	54.6	55.9
0.01 N	50.0	49.5	49.8
0.02 N	45.7	48.1	46.4
0.05 N	45.8	46.2	46.0
0.05 N	47.2	47.4	47.3
0.1 N	47.6	48.5	48.1
0.1 N	46.9	48.8	47.9
0.04 N	46.2	47.8	47.0
0.1 N	41.4	42.6	42.0

TABLE XII.

*Sodium Citrate.**Temp. 35°.*

Electrolyte concentration	Rate of migration		
	Direct	Reverse	Mean
0	47.80	48.7	48
† 0.0005 N	46.1	48.5	46.3
0.001 N	49.2	48.4	48.8
0.02 N	49.7	50.7	50.2
0.1 N	51.8	50.6	51.2
0.1 N	46.6	49	47.6

† This initial decrease has been confirmed with another sol.

TABLE XIII.

*Potassium Ferrocyanide.**Temp. 35°*

Electrolyte concentra- tion	Rate of migration		
	Direct	Reverse	Mean
0	61.5	57.9	59.7
·004 N	57.5	55.9	56.7
·01 N	66.2	66.3	66.2
·03 N	66.8	63.2	65

We find that in the case of hydrochloric acid and potassium chloride there is a decrease in the charge at all concentrations. Sodium benzoate shows two maxima followed by the usual decrease. Sodium citrate shows an initial decrease followed by an increase. The charge again diminishes. Potassium ferrocyanide shows an initial decrease and then an increase which persists upto the highest concentrations recorded. The initial variations with these three electrolytes are complex probably because of interactions between the anions in the surface and those in the added electrolyte including hydroxyl ions which are likely to be present as a result of hydrolysis at least in the case of the benzoate and the citrate (*cf. Mukherjee and Chaudhury, loc. cit.*). Sodium citrate and potassium ferrocyanide show a higher charge than that of the pure sol upto a concentration of 0.01 N and 0.03 N respectively. Considering the effect of these electrolytes on the charge alone and comparing equivalent concentrations we find that potassium ferrocyanide ought to have the greatest stabilising effect, sodium benzoate coming next after it followed by sodium citrate. The chloride ion is comparatively weakly adsorbed.

We would refer here to the following earlier measurements with sodium and lithium chlorides which show that there is actually an increase in the negative charge at low concentration in the case of lithium and sodium chlorides and that the initial increase is

The measurements for the concentrations 0.00025 N and 0.01 N in the case of potassium chloride show a greater divergence between the direct and reverse movements than in the case of the others.

greater for lithium than for sodium ; whereas we have just observed that potassium chloride and hydrochloric acid show a diminution at all the concentrations studied.

TABLE XIV.

Sodium Chloride.

Conc. of the electrolyte	Rate of migration
0	51
·00005 N	57·8
·0001 N	54·2
·0002 N	48·7
·001 N	45·4
·02 N	39·8

TABLE XV.

Lithium Chloride.

Conc. of the electrolyte.	Rate of migration
0	51
·00005 N	59·7
·0001 N	55·1
·0005 N	47
·005 N	43·5

Regarding the interpretation of this rise in the rate we would refer to the considerations set forth by Mukherjee and Iyer (*J. Ind.*

Indian Chem. Soc., 1926, 3, 307,) which show that the initial rise is to be ascribed to the adsorption of chlorine ions.

IV. *Variation of Charge with Mixtures of Electrolytes.*

TABLE XVI.

Sodium chloride and sodium benzoate Temp. 35°

Conc. of sodium chloride.	Conc. of sodium benzoate	Rate of migration.		
		Direct.	Reverse	Mean.
0	0	54.7	56	55.4
.005 N	0	43.5	43.3	43.4
..	.001 N	46.7	46.2	46.5
..	.002 N	44.4	45.4	44.9
..	.005 N	37.6	37.7	37.7
..	.01 N	33	33.0	33.5

TABLE XVII.

Sodium chloride and sodium Oxalate Temp. 35°.

Conc. of sodium chloride.	Conc. of sodium oxalate.	Rate of migration.		
		Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	0	54.7	56	55.4
.005 N	0	43.5	43.3	43.4
..	.001 N	46.2	48.3	47.3
..	.002 N	44.9	45.8	45.1
..	.005 N	43	45	44
..	.01 N	40.4	42.6	41.6

TABLE XVIII.

Sodium chloride and sodium citrate Temp. 85°.

Conc. of sodium chloride.	Conc. of sodium citrate.	Rate of migration.		
		Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	0	54.7	56	55.4
.005 N	0	43.5	43.3	43.4
..	.001 N	43.8	43.1	43.5
..	.002 N	47.8	48.6	48.2
..	.005 N	44.9	43.8	44.4
..	.1 N	36.2	37.6	36.9

TABLE XIX.

Barium Chloride and Sodium Benzoate. Temp. 85°.

Conc. of barium chloride.	Conc. of sodium benzoate.	Rate of migration.		
		Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	0	55.5	51.5	53.5
.001 N	0	20.7	19.7	20.2
..	.034 N	40.9	40.7	40.8
..	.0567 N	45.3	45.4	45.4
..	.085 N	45	43.4	44.2
..	.1184 N	40.8*	41.2*	41
..	..	40.6*	(?) 38.1*	36.9
..	..	40.2*	40.2*	40.2

TABLE XX.

Calcium Benzoate and Sodium Benzoate. Temp. 35°.

Conc. of calcium benzoate	Conc. of sodium benzoate.	Rate of migration.		
		Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	0	55.5	51.5	53.5
·0015 N	0	9.6	8.5	9.1
"	·034 N	38.6	38.9	38.7
"	·0587 N	47.4	46	46.7
"	·086 N	44.8	45.0	45.4
"	·1134 N	35.9*	37.4*	35.2

TABLE XXI.

Barium chloride and sodium chloride. Temp. 35°.

Conc. of barium chloride.	Conc. of Sodium chloride.	Rate of migration.		
		Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	0	55.5	51.5	53.5
·001 N	0	20.7	19.7	20.3
"	·015 N	36.8	37.7	37.3
"	·025 N	40.0	37.6	40.3
"	·0375 N	38.4	40.0	39.7
"	·05 N	The sol coagulated on admixture.		

* In these cases a curious effect was observed. Although the charge was much greater than that for the single electrolyte, an appreciable amount of the sol coagulated in the tube while measurement was being taken.

TABLE XXII.

Magnesium chloride and sodium chloride. Temp. 35°.

Conc. of magnesium chloride.	Conc. of sodium chloride.	Rate of migration.		
		D' rect.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	0	61·5	57·9	59·7
·0015 N	0	15	16	15·6
..	·015 N	32·4	33·9	33·2
..	·025 N	42·4	42·4	42·4
..	·0375 N	48·1	42	42·6
..	·05 N	The sol coagulated on admixture.		

TABLE XXIII.

Magnesium chloride and Lithium chloride. Temp. 35°.

Conc. of magnesium chloride.	Conc. of lithium chloride.	Rate of migration.		
		Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.
0	0	61·5	57·9	59·7
·0015 N	0	15	16	15·6
..	·016 N	24·9	27·2	26·1
..	·027 N	46·0	45·2	46·1
..	·04 N	51·5	49·2	50·4

TABLE XXIV.

Potassium chloride and Potassium ferrocyanide. Temp. 35°.

Conc. of potassium chloride.	Conc. of potassium ferrocyanide.	Rate of migration.		Mean.
		Direct.	Reverse.	
0	0	61.5	57.9	59.7
.004 N	0	50.3	50.1	50.2
..	.004 N	60.6	59	59.8
..	.01 N	49	49.3	49.2
..	.03 N	The sol coagulated.		

Attention has of late been directed to the problem of finding an explanation for the so-called ionic antagonism which plays an important part in the biological sciences (*cf.* Freundlich and Scholz, *Koll. Beih.*, (1922), 14, 267; Mukherjee and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). Investigations dealing with the general aspects of the problem of coagulation of colloids by mixtures of electrolytes have been also carried out by Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, (1921), 25, 665, 28, 232, (1924), (1926) 30, 20. and (1926) 30, 1527), Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, (1925) 29, 435 and 659), and Sen (*z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 149, 130; *J. Phys. Chem.*, (1925) 29, 517. and by Kruyt and Willigen (*K. Akad. Wentensch, Amsterdam*, (1926) 29, 484).

The experimental work on this subject has centred round measurements of coagulating values and some limited measurements of adsorption of the ions of the electrolytes, mostly carried out by Weiser. The absence of measurements of charges has already been commented upon. Mukherjee and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) first worked with mixtures of electrolytes having a common cation and concluded (p. 220) "that even in cases where the displacement of adsorption of one cation by another is not possible the effect of the anion is as pronounced as in the case where displacement of

adsorption may occur in addition." They also state (p. 223) "the initial rise in charge at low electrolyte concentrations is to a large extent responsible for all these effects."

From the data given above we find that there is evidence of an initial increase in the charge on the addition of citrate, benzoate and ferrocyanide. In each of the Tables from XVI to XXIV the charge of the colloidal particles under the following conditions have been given :

(a) without any electrolyte, (b) with only the electrolyte whose concentration remains fixed, and (c) with different concentrations of the second electrolyte.

A comparison of the charges under conditions (a), (b) and (c) just mentioned shows that there is a rise in the charge when the concentration of the second electrolyte is small. When the two electrolytes have a cation in common, there is no question of a displacement of adsorption of one cation by another. In the case of benzoate (Table XI) the increase in the charge leaves no doubt as to its greater adsorption than that of the chloride ion. In the case of the oxalate (Table XVII) and the citrate (Table XII) though there is no doubt that some of the anions originally present in the primary layer are displaced by them, the rise as such constitutes no evidence as to their greater adsorbability than say the chloride ion, for a slight displacement will increase the negative charge because of their greater valencies. Some displacement can be expected even if their adsorbability is smaller. In Tables XIX to XXIII the electrolyte with a fixed concentration contains a cation of higher valency. In Table XIX there are two cations and two anions and in Tables XX to XXIII we have a common anion. *The displacement of the adsorption of a divalent cation (barium or calcium) in the fixed sheet of the double layer by sodium ions is definitely proved from the data recorded in the three Tables XX to XXII and we are dealing with an interchange of ions in the double layer of the type referred to by Mukherjee and Iyer (loc. cit). That magnesium is more weakly adsorbed than barium is evident from their respective effect on sodium chloride.*

From Tables XXII and XIII (see also Fig. 1) we find that at low concentrations lithium has a smaller effect on the displacement of the adsorption of magnesium ions than sodium has in keeping with its lower adsorbability. In discussing these cases of displacement of adsorption on the basis of the variation in the charge we have to

remember that besides the relative adsorbability we have to consider the valencies. Considering the portion of the lithium chloride curve below that of sodium chloride we see that though the displacement of the adsorption of magnesium chloride by lithium is less, as the concentration of the lithium chloride rises, the displacement increases and on account of the weaker adsorbability of the lithium ions, which begins to be felt more and more strongly from about a concentration of .016 N., the negative charge rises abruptly until it passes over the curve of sodium chloride. At higher concentrations the relatively greater adsorbability of sodium ions lowers the negative charge to a greater extent.

In Table XXIV we have a common cation and two different anions. The increase in the charge on the addition of potassium ferrocyanide shows clearly the primary adsorption of the ferrocyanide ions. It does not mean however that the adsorption of ferrocyanide ion is considerably stronger than that of chloride ion as there is a difference in valency. The adsorption of the ferrocyanide ion would seem to be stronger than what appears to be the case from the above data if the concentrations are expressed in terms of gram ions and not in terms of gram equivalents.

From the above we see that both the displacement of the cation and the adsorption of the anion have to be considered in explaining the coagulation of colloids by mixtures of electrolytes. Also that both these factors affect the coagulating concentration of the second electrolyte through an increase in the negative charge of the primary layer.

V. Relation between Charge and Coagulating Concentration.

Regarding however the relationships between the charge and the coagulating concentrations we find that these are not simple. We would like to point out that in many cases it was noted that the sol to which two electrolytes have been added coagulated although the charge of the particle was much higher than in the absence of the second electrolyte (*vide* Tables XXI and XXII, c.p. also XX). Obviously the stability is not so directly related to the charge as is generally believed to be the case. Thus the electrolytes with divalent cations depress the charge enormously. We have stable sols with these electrolytes where the particles show a rate of migration

ranging from 20 to as far as low as 9 (calcium benzoate). From the slope of the curve with potassium, sodium or lithium chloride as the added electrolyte it would appear that coagulation takes place before a velocity of about 20 has been reached. We would particularly refer to the low charge with calcium benzoate.

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